

Building and Sustaining Data Analytics Internships at Sinclair Community College

Introduction

Internships are a cornerstone of the Data Analytics Program at [Sinclair Community College](#). Since 2011, the program has started with a one-year certificate designed to skill up workforce employees and has started with integrated internships as a way to connect classroom learning with real-world experience, strengthen regional industry partnerships, and prepare students for evolving workforce needs. For program directors seeking to build or strengthen their own internship models, Sinclair's approach offers a framework focused on collaboration, student preparation, and sustainable employer relationships.

Program Structure

The Data Analytics Program offers a one-year [Data Analytics Certificate](#) (33 credit hours) and a two-year [Associate of Applied Science Degree in Data Analytics](#) (65 credit hours) that emphasizes workforce readiness, data literacy, skills-based learning, and Experiential-Based and Project-Based Learning (PBL) through industry collaboration. Both paths require students to complete an internship to graduate. The Data Analytics Program has two additional certificates that are entry points for high school programs (dual credit) and career-shifting practitioners to gain skills without internships, but are designed to be stackable certificates leading to the Associates.

PROJECT-BASED LEARNING

To prepare students for internships, the Data Analytics Program integrates project-based (sometimes service-based learning) and experiential learning into courses. Faculty mentors and [Work-Based Learning \(WBL\)](#) staff encourage students to attend networking events and peer

groups to build professional relationships. Many data courses, like Introduction to Data Literacy, Data Visualization, Database Management, and PBL, incorporate the kinds of tasks students will face during internships and professional settings. Rather than focusing only on abstracted theory, students work on applied projects that require them to analyze real-world data sets, design interactive dashboards in Tableau to communicate insights, and build fully functioning databases for real business and non-profit needs. These experiences give students a chance to practice problem-solving, teamwork, and communication in professional contexts, helping them to develop confidence and readiness for internships and careers.

INTERSHIP DETAILS:

- **Duration:** Internships run 8–16 weeks, requiring a minimum of 150 hours per term (about 10-20 hours per week). Fall and Spring internships are usually 16 weeks, while Summer internships are usually 12 weeks. Internships can extend past a term.
- **Eligibility:** Students must complete at least 50% of their academic program and maintain a 2.0 GPA to participate in an internship. This ensures a strong technical foundation before entering the workplace.
- **Oversight:** The internship program is managed by the Office of Work-Based Learning, which handles external partnerships, compliance, and student career preparation. Faculty associated with the Data Analytics Program and the internship course coordinator serve as mentors for student interns.
- **Student compensation:** In exceptional cases where the host organization is unable to compensate interns, WBL leverages institutional funding, state and local grants, and the federal work-study program to remove financial barriers for students seeking internships. Most student internships are paid.

KEY RESOURCES AND SUPPORT:

- Time for the Data Analytics Program faculty to design the curriculum and engage with external partners.
- Industry engagement through advisory boards.
- Institutional support from the Experiential Services Director and staff at WBL and Career Services for scheduling, outreach, and student career preparation.
- Software and vendor tools like KNIME, Tableau, MySQL, Microsoft, Oracle, SAS, and MongoDB to prepare students for real-world projects.
- Partnerships with local organizations that host professional networking events for students and faculty.
- External funding from the National Science Foundation (NSF), state and local budgets, and (soon) the Sinclair Foundation.

Partnership Development

Sinclair uses three strategies to cultivate and sustain industry partnerships:

1. INDUSTRY ADVISORY BOARDS

Just prior to 2016, the Data Analytics Program formed an advisory board with regional employers to align its curriculum with workforce needs. Later, through a project that was funded by the [National Science Foundation \(NSF\)](#) ([Award #1501927](#)), the industry advisory board was reengaged through a symposium to validate the knowledge, skills, and abilities (KSAs) of data analytics. The project was completed in 2021. The Data Analytics Program continues to seek feedback through an advisory board using the [BILT \(Business & Industry Leadership Team\) model](#), which ensures that students learn technical skills and the competencies employers prioritize. This BILT model will be used to develop the Data Analytics Program's new Applied AI offerings. The Data Analytics Program also collaborates with Sinclair's Experiential Services Director to integrate community-oriented and nonprofit-aligned projects within courses like database management and data visualization.

2. FACULTY-DRIVEN OUTREACH

Faculty within the Data Analytics Program attend local conferences, networking peer-events, and industry association meetings (e.g., [Technology First](#); [Strategic Ohio Council for Higher Education \(SOCHE\)](#); the [Dayton Area Chamber of Commerce](#)) to learn about employers' needs and engage potential partners for the advisory and internship program. The Data Analytics Program also hosts local data events, such as [DataFest](#) and DataJam, encourages peer events, day conferences, and regional events, and invites local industry partners and data practitioners to serve as mentors to student teams for DataFest.

3. DEDICATED STAFF SUPPORT

If an industry contact shows interest in sponsoring a Data Analytics Program intern, faculty connect interested contacts to the WBL, which provides information about the application process and ensures that the internship opportunity is academically aligned.

Process at a glance:

1. Employers submit a [New Internships form](#) and complete an [Employer Application and Outreach form](#).
2. WBL ensures compliance with state/federal requirements.
3. Faculty review internship expectations for academic alignment.
4. Employers, faculty, and students sign agreements before internship placement begins.

On average, the process takes about 4-8 months. If a host organization cannot afford to compensate an intern but can offer valuable experience, Sinclair leverages stipends, its federal work-study program, or grant funds to ensure equitable access.

Student Preparation

Internship placements are not guaranteed, as hiring decisions ultimately rest with the host organizations. Before students are connected with employers, students undergo structured preparation through WBL that could include:

- Student background assessment to assess needs and career aspirations
- Resume reviews
- Cover letter workshops
- Interview preparation and mock interviews
- Strengths assessments

Through authentic project-based experiences, students strengthen both technical skills and professional habits, gaining exposure to workplace-like challenges that build confidence and readiness. This approach creates a clear bridge between classroom preparation and the internships, outcomes, and long-term career benefits that follow.

Benefits & Outcomes

Data Analytics Program internships are a critical pathway to employment for students, including placements with regional employers such as Winsupply, CareSource, Great American Insurance Group, and Dayton Children's and Premier Health, among others. The program is designed to provide value for all parties involved—students, faculty, and employers alike—by creating a feedback loop between education and industry. Students gain career experience and professional networks, faculty gain insight into evolving workforce needs, and employers benefit from early access to well-prepared talent.

- **For students:** Direct career pathways, exposure to professional networks, and in many cases, job offers post-internship. As a testament to the program's success, four alumni shared their journey through the program and how it prepared them for life after graduation in this [video: Students like You](#).
- **For faculty:** Insights into evolving workforce needs and trends that inform curriculum.
- **For employers:** Workforce-ready graduates, early access to talent, opportunities to influence curriculum, and collaborative community impact.
- **For Sinclair:** Positive reputation as a regional partner for workforce development and helping students land roles.

Challenges & Future Directions

One ongoing challenge is employers' preference for students in 4-year programs. To counter this bias, the Data Analytics Program aligns its curricula with workforce needs and has established transfer agreements with four-year institutions for students who wish to continue their training upon earning their associate's degree or certificate. Sinclair also engages in advocacy to increase awareness of this bias and partners with local groups, including the Dayton Foundation, to help unlock this barrier regionally. Looking forward, the Data Analytics Program aims to deepen its relationships with regional employers, expand experiential learning (e.g., expanding service-based projects with nonprofits; apprenticeships), and enable students to responsibly incorporate evolving technologies, such as generative AI tools, into their workflows. The Data Analytics Program is partnering with the [National Applied AI Consortium \(NAAIC\)](#) to expand its AI curriculum in the form of an Applied AI certificate. The Data Analytics Program also has plans to expand its service-oriented curricula by working with partners at research-intensive, four-year institutions to adapt and integrate Data for Good pedagogy that speaks to the unique skills and career aspirations of Sinclair's student population. In the meantime, WBL aims to educate organizations on the value of data analytics interns who receive guidance from subject matter experts (faculty).

Practical Guidance for Program Leaders

The Data Analytics Program at Sinclair Community College offers several insights for data science program leaders who are preparing students for successful careers.

1. **Establish a dedicated office or point person:** Course and partnership coordinators are crucial for building and maintaining relationships with external organizations and ensuring compliance and alignment.
2. **Leverage college administrators and faculty networks:** Faculty connections often open the first door to employers. Faculty can broker initial connections with employers through conferences and networking events. They are often also the most familiar students' needs and capabilities. Pairing faculty with a WBL liaison ensures both academic and operational alignment.
3. **Engage nonprofit partners as soon as possible:** Engage nonprofit partners early to provide students with service-learning and community-based project opportunities.
4. **Prepare well-rounded students:** Strong communication and collaboration skills complement technical training. Students should seek out career centers and advisors for resources and individualized feedback several months before they apply to internships.

5. **Secure funding:** Use internal budgets, endowments and foundations, state/local grants, and federal work-study to remove financial barriers for students seeking internships.
6. **Track outcomes:** Centralized software can help manage agreements, evaluations, and reporting for meaningful data tracking for external parties like state and federal agencies.
7. **Form advisory boards:** Industry input aligns curriculum with employer needs and can open partnerships, internships, and job opportunities.

Contact

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Suggested Citation

Min, S., Parker, M., & Van Tuyl, S. (2025). *Building and Sustaining Data Analytics Internships at Sinclair Community College* [White Paper]. Alliance for Data Science and AI (ADSA).

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the following for generously sharing their time, insights, and feedback on this case study. Their reviews and comments helped ensure the accuracy and clarity of the final version.

- Paul Hansford, Sinclair Community College
- Jackie Duffy, Sinclair Community College
- Jeffrey Amberly, Sinclair Community College
- Angela Fernandez, Sinclair Community College
- Kelly Vogelsong, Sinclair Community College

